

CASE REPORT

Orthodontic management of a patient with Class I malocclusion and crowding: A case report

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Abstract

This case reports the orthodontic treatment of a 12-year-old male patient with Class I malocclusion and minor crowding in both maxillary and mandibular arches with a posterior crossbite. Orthodontic treatment was done comprehensively using sagittal appliance on the maxillary arch which was used to advance the maxillary incisors and to distalize the maxillary molar by increasing arch length. Standard metal braces were also used on the upper and the lower arches for tooth alignment and improvement of bite. Second molars were removed in each quadrant to relieve crowding. Remarkable results were already seen after over a year of treatment. Thus, it is concluded that the use of sagittal appliances, metal braces, and removal of all second molars yield better and stable results in the treatment of Class I malocclusion with minor crowding.

Keywords malocclusion, crowding, crossbite, Angle Class I

1 | Introduction

Class I malocclusion as defined by Angle, incorporates the normal relationship of the molars but differs in the arrangement of teeth relative to the line of occlusion.³ One of the most common occlusal features in this case of malocclusion is crowding in both maxillary and mandibular arches.¹ Class I malocclusion is by far the most

prevalent type of malocclusion worldwide.² Females have a higher prevalence of anterior crowding than males, and malalignment is greater in the maxilla than mandible. Multiple etiological factors result in crowding but in this case, space loss and tooth movement are the primary reasons. Crowding occurs when there is a discrepancy between the size of teeth

and the size of the arches.³ Understanding the etiology of the case is fundamentally important in determining the treatment and post-treatment methods that will be most effective.³

Crowding is a common esthetic complaint of patients seeking orthodontic treatment as the anterior teeth are visible during a smile. Any misalignment could affect patients' well-being and quality of life.² There are two main approaches in treating Class I malocclusion: extraction and the use of orthodontic appliances.⁴ In case of severe crowding, extraction is used to address crowding and reduce protrusion of the teeth and overlying soft tissues. Fixed orthodontic appliances are indicated when precise

tooth control and multiple tooth movements in one arch are required.⁴ This case report aims to describe the orthodontic treatment's progress of class I malocclusion with severe crowding with the extraction of second molars and application of fixed orthodontic appliance.

2 | Case presentation section

2.1 Chief complaint and history

A 12-year-old male patient complained of crowding on both upper and lower teeth. However, frontal proportions were normal. Verbal probing indicated that he was unhappy with the aesthetics of his smile because of the overlapping of teeth. He has mentioned that his appearance has

Figure 1. (A) Dentition before orthodontic treatment (B) Panoramic radiograph (C) Computation using Pont's index for prediction of maxillary bicuspid measurement for adequate space

Table 1. Steps and procedure of treatment plan with duration of treatment

STEP	PROCEDURE	DURATION
1	Scaling and polishing Use of maxillary sagittal appliance	2-3 weeks
2	Placement of standard metal appliances on mandibular and maxillary teeth except on #13 and #23 Stop locks on #16 and #26	1 day
3	Adjustment (alignment and leveling)	13 months
4	Open coil springs in between #12 and #14 Open coil springs in between #22 and #24	8 months
5	Placement of standard metal appliances on #13 and #23	1 day
6	Adjustment (alignment and leveling of #13 and #16)	9 months
7	Extraction of all second molars	6 weeks
8	Remove stop locks on #16 and #26 Open coil springs in between #15 and #16, #25 and #26	4 months
9	Placement of stop locks on #16 and #26 Open coil springs in between #14 and #15, #24 and #25	4 months
10	Open coil springs in between #13 and #14, #23 and #24	4 months
11	Placement of heavier stainless steel wires	12 months
12	Removal of wire	3 months
13	Removal of standard metal appliances	1 day

affected the way his peers interacted with him which in return influenced his self-esteem. The patient saw his dentist at least once every three years. His medical history was unremarkable. He brushed once daily and did not floss.

2.2 Diagnosis

Upon examination, the primary clinical findings indicated that maxillary and mandibular teeth were crowded. Maxillary canines were positioned more superiorly and the mesial incline of the upper canines overlap the distal slope of the lower canine. The

maxillary and mandibular anterior teeth were rotated and there was evidence of misalignment. Crossbite at the area of teeth #25, #35, and #36 (Figure 1A). The panoramic radiograph has shown that all third molars were present but had not yet erupted (Figure 1B). No evidence of overbite or flaring. No deviation of mandible or clicking present.

An arch analysis was done using the Pont's index.¹¹ The interpremolar arch width was 36mm but the maxillary bicuspid measurement for adequate space was equal to 39mm. There was a

3mm shortage of space indicating minor crowding (Figure 1C).

Clinical findings indicated that the patient had a Class I malocclusion with minor crowding.

2.3 Prognosis

During the dental consultation with the patient, alternative treatment plans for his case were discussed. It was planned to relieve the maxillary and mandibular crowding and to achieve optimal occlusal alignment. Orthodontics using fixed appliance therapy and the use of temporary anchorage devices for molar distalization was recommended. Based on the treatment plan, the skill of the dentist, and the patient's compliance, the prognosis is excellent.

2.4 Treatment

With consent from the patient, the treatment included orthodontics (Table 1). The aim was to increase arch length to relieve crowding of anterior teeth and improve occlusal alignment. The orthodontic treatment objectives were to create space to allow movement in anterior teeth, correct rotation and alignment of teeth #12, #11, #21, #22, #32, #31, #41, and #42, correct crossbite at the area of #25 and #35, open room for teeth #13 and #23 to improve canine relationship, achieve root parallelism of the adjacent teeth, utilize second molar

Figure 2. Maxillary sagittal appliance

replacement with third molar, and use natural teeth movement to establish stability.

Treatment was performed with orthodontics using fixed appliance therapy and TADs (Temporary Anchorage Devices). The patient first used a maxillary sagittal appliance for molar distalization (Figure 2). He was then placed on upper and lower standard metal appliances with sequentially larger wires to align and level arches. A nickel-titanium open coil springs were applied to move individual teeth. For stabilization, heavier stainless-steel wires were utilized.

Treatment started with molar distalization using a maxillary sagittal appliance. Adjustments were done every two days alternately. Screw was unwounded on the left and two days after the right screw was unwounded (four days per side). Adjustments were done in two to three weeks. Metal standard appliances were then placed on upper and lower teeth except on

teeth #13 and #23. To prevent further distalization of molars, stop locks were placed on #16 and #26. Alignment and leveling were done with sequentially larger wires in thirteen months. NiTi open coil springs were used to force back #12, #14, #22, and #24. This created an open space for teeth #13 and #23. Standard metal appliances were placed on #13 and #23 to allow alignment and leveling. In the next appointment, teeth #17 and #47 were extracted. Teeth #27 and #37 were extracted a week after. After allowing the wound to heal, stop locks were removed and teeth #16 and #26 were pushed back using open coil springs for four months. Same procedure was done with #15, #25 and #14, #24 however with stop locks on #16 and #26 to avoid further movement. Heavier stainless-steel wires were utilized to improve alignment, leveling, and stability. After a year, wires were removed to permit natural tooth

movement or relapse. Braces were then removed three months after.

2.5 Outcome and post-treatment

After orthodontic treatment, there was an increase in arch length, occlusal alignment has greatly improved, rotated #12, #11, #21, #22, #42, #41, #31, #32, and crossbite at the area of #25 and #35 have been corrected. Canine relationships have improved. Upper canines' distal inclines overlap mesial slopes of the lower canines, and root parallelism of adjacent teeth was achieved.

One-year post-treatment, there was no evidence of crowding relapse even without the use of retainer (Figure 3A). Four years post-treatment, the dentition's stability was confirmed as no obvious relapse had taken place and erupting third molars were starting to replace the second molars (Figure 3B).

Figure 3. Figure 3. (A) 1 year post-treatment and (B) 4 years post-treatment

3 | Discussion

Dento-maxillary disharmony presents with many clinical signs that allow for early diagnosis. The type of disharmony, its severity, and its etiology guide the therapeutic choice from among the management of the space, the expansion of the arches, or the realization of planned extractions. There are two suggested treatment protocols for Class I malocclusion: non-extraction or extraction. In non-extraction, space is gained with stripping, expansion, derotation, uprighting, or distalization. On the other hand, extraction is usually done with the upper/lower second premolar, or with asymmetric extraction or single tooth extraction.⁵

In this case, Pont's index was used to determine the severity of the crowding. ⁶This analysis will indicate whether there is a need for second molar replacement or third molar extraction. The interpremolar arch width was 36mm, but the maxillary bicuspid measurement for adequate space was equal to 39mm, so there was a 3mm shortage of space, indicating minor crowding. ⁸

They decided to extract the second molars since third molars can be used to replace a first or second molar that will be extracted in this case. Teeth #17, #27, #37, #47 was indicated to be extracted. This will allow space for the movement of teeth.⁹

In this case, molar distalization was done first by the use of a maxillary sagittal appliance. This is an active plate with expansion screws in the anteroposterior direction, hence the name. It is used to advance the maxillary incisors and to distalize the maxillary molars, thereby increasing arch length, and stop locks were placed on first molars afterward to prevent movements.¹⁰ Aligning and leveling of arches were done by the use of sequentially larger wires. After treatment, crowding of anterior teeth was relieved, optimal occlusal alignment has been attained, and the patient was satisfied with the treatment. This clearly shows that the objectives of the treatment plan were achieved.

4 | Conclusions

Maxillary sagittal appliance and standard metal appliance are the primary steps in managing a 12-year-old patient with class I malocclusion. Treatment started with molar distalization using a maxillary sagittal appliance to increase the dental arch length as well as to relieve crowding of anterior teeth. Standard metal appliances were then placed on upper and lower teeth for correct occlusal alignment and leveling. Furthermore, to prevent relapse of the crowding, extraction of the second molars were done to give space and allow the teeth to be pushed back thus to have space

for the erupting third molars. After treatment, the dental arch length is then equivalent to the substantial arch length accompanied by the Pont's index with the result of significant measurement of the maxillary bicuspid. It is important to calculate the dental arch length and maxillary bicuspid measurement by applying the Pont's index before treatment to achieve the proper diagnostic procedure in the treatment of malocclusion.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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